

The Big Gulp
by Brian Paul Kaess

Garret loved to drink Bug Gulps, you know the ones you buy at 7-Eleven,
He'd gather two handfuls of pennies, and he'd be left in pure Heaven,
For it was not only the caffeine from the Diet Coke he craved,
But also those chocolate Eclairs from which he was mightily enslaved,
As a young College student, he believed glucose would help him on exams,
So that enough candy bars might help him with all those chemistry diagrams,
7-Eleven was on the corner of Clark & Olive, not far from where Victor took a hit,
Garret being the omnipresent corner boy, that didn't bother him a bit,
For he cruised to all the convenience stores, in search of diet-coke,
He was such a dashing figure, he should've worn a cloak,
It was at Pierce School basketball court, where he followed another dream,
Playing street basketball at night with Tripp & others, rising high and supreme,
For they were the Lords of the playlot, who would 'bring it' up the court,
Violence, though not uncommon, was but a last resort,
He steered from trouble as best he could,
And formed a bond with street basketball players, not unlike a brotherhood,
All these times, he would bring his Big Gulp along,
And park it alongside the court, pennies and all!
That's when the cops answered a disturbance call,
And almost ferried the Kaess' away from it all,
But Brian's insistence had saved the day,
So that the Twins didn't become part of the urban decay,
So Garret went on to do mightily fine on exams,
He was studying so hard, he could write his own epigrams,
Thus a student-journalist at Truman he became,
And then a scholarship at Roosevelt he now took aim,
Where he earned it just in the nick of time,
For with just \$50 a month from his brother, he couldn't spare a dime,
Garret went on to graduate summa cum laude,
And so with the help of Big Gulps & chocolate eclairs, he had gained wide applause,
And managed to triumph over it all!